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PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION AND ITS ESSENCE

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***Annotation:** Pedagogical communication is a conversation organized by a pedagogue with his team, parents, colleagues and management in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical etiquette and communication. Pedagogical communication culture, which forms the basis of the teacher's skills, is manifested in the process of communication with the team of students, parents, colleagues, and management. In this case, the interaction of the pedagogue with the group of students is especially important. The pedagogue strives to communicate with the students and make it effective.*

***Keywords:** teacher, pedagogue, mastered, cultural, personal, wealth, individual.*

***Аннотация:** Педагогическое общение – это беседа, организованная педагогом со своим коллективом, родителями, коллегами и руководством в соответствии с требованиями педагогического этикета и общения. Культура педагогического общения, составляющая основу умений учителя, проявляется в процессе общения с коллективом учащихся, родителей, коллег, руководства. В этом случае особенно важно взаимодействие педагога с группой обучающихся. Педагог стремится общаться со студентами и сделать это эффективным.*

***Ключевое слово:** учитель, педагог, освоенный, культурный, личный, материальный, индивидуальный.*

The opinions expressed by children in the process of communication, their views, provide an opportunity for a close study of a person. Getting to know the student's personality closely, being aware of his inner experiences, thoughts, feelings, dreams, goals and aspirations in life means the methodical and psychologically correct organization of the pedagogical process. provides After all, in this process, the pedagogue organizes activities taking into account the age, psychological and personal characteristics of the person being educated. The exchange of information in the communication process ensures that the participants of the educational process exchange information about social processes and personal development. Establishing cooperation between pedagogy and children creates conditions for effective exchange of information between them in any situation. In this process, the teacher becomes the closest advisor, guide and leader of students. During communication, it is necessary to pay serious attention to ensure that the students adequately assess their identity, "me", and value, and strive forward with life goals set before them. In the process of communication, the task of exchanging information is carried out using certain tools.

In the organization of pedagogical activities, not only the teacher himself, but also the students should master the culture of communication based on his positive influence. The task of professional-pedagogical communication is to master the technology, in which the pedagogue can use warm relations, as a result of which the personality of the pedagogue is revealed. The communicative culture of the educator plays an important role in the success of the professional-pedagogical dialogue. The child should feel that the teacher is speaking from the heart. Otherwise, communication will not be possible. Some pedagogues communicate with children regardless of their age. If the teacher notices that the child is growing up, this indicates that he is forming a culture of communication. In order to achieve communicative culture, the teacher should pay attention to the following:

- the culture of patiently listening to the child;
- listen carefully to the child, even if it is not interesting to him;
- sensing that the child is bored, turning the topic to another interesting direction;
- try to raise the child's mood before talking;

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